

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KIM****FIRST NAME: UN YONG****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Fundamentals of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 12-16)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-22)
3. Differences between American and UK English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style Guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I am excited to embark on my Ph.D. journey with the course ACA-401D at EUCLID. To my surprise, the ACA-401D course pack provided by EUCLID is more comprehensive in terms of its content than I thought, as my previous master's degree courses never delved into such niceties of academic essay writing. I guess this is where I see the difference between Ph.D. and a master's degree.

Having reviewed the general course outline, I realized how rigorous it is to develop one academic essay. The course material outlines ABCs of essential concepts needed to start writing a good one. As this is certainly more than a simple refresher course for the English language, I took mental notes of where I will refer if I were to review my essay.

This paper discusses the essentials of academic essay writing and the components required to achieve a coherent essay. In addition, I discuss the grammar aspects of an essay, such as punctuation, language style coherence, the importance of not committing plagiarism, and the use of style guides.

2) ESSENTIALS OF ESSAY WRITING

Writing an essay seemed daunting, but with a few tips in mind, I understand that a good essay has a proper structure and is to be reviewed after being written. It is always advisable to start thinking and writing as early as possible, to define parameters within the essay, and to come up with a research plan in terms of timeline and content (EUCLID 2021, 7).

a) **Structuring an essay**

An academic paper begins by looking deeper into what the question asks, which is why “analyzing the question and defining key terms” is at the bottom of the pyramid (EUCLID 2021, 8). Preparatory work before getting hands down to write something involves nothing more than previewing and taking extensive notes on other academic work and various sources of information (EUCLID 2021, 8). At this stage, identifying what the writer does not know comes through reflecting on the rationale behind writing an essay, the relevance of a particular topic being discussed, and its usefulness of supporting evidence (EUCLID 2021, 9).

Drafting rough answers to the question can be a starting point for gathering and synthesizing the writer's ideas. Usually, these ideas will be processed into three parts – introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 9). All kinds of content can be organized into these three main parts, making a particular argument more coherent.

b) **Editing an essay**

When I was reading through the course pack, it struck me how important it is to leave some time before submitting a paper. While it is important to have structural pillars of a draft essay, it is also important to review them after a few days so that the writer can look at the essay with fresh perspectives (EUCLID 2021, 12). This editing process also involves emotions, to my utter surprise. Being more composed when editing gives the writer a higher chance to produce better quality work than being less composed (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The punctuation section from the course pack is essentially a refresher grammar course for the English language, but its content is not to be considered light. For example, in the sentence "She was eight months pregnant when she went into labor," I thought there should be an apostrophe behind the word "months," which was not the case (EUCLID 2021, 16). Another notable instance is not using a comma after a time-based adverbial phrase, such as “In 2010 the most popular game ... was hopscotch.” – I kept thinking there should be a comma right after the year “2010” (EUCLID 2021, 19).

4) AMERICAN AND UK ENGLISH - DIFFERENCE

I have come to appreciate the differences the American and UK English. Even as I write this response paper, I find these differences particularly confusing regarding quotation marks. However, I believe I can pave the way for a clean, well-organized academic paper by understanding the subtle differences in terms of inserting quotation marks (EUCLID 2016, 8:40-8:50).

Although I am sticking to American English for now, I should strive to understand the UK English style for my comprehension in the literature review of my doctoral thesis later.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is undoubtedly a severe offense as it compromises academic integrity (EUCLID 2021, 34). In my view, mentioning and paraphrasing a source is a minimum etiquette the writer must adhere to when presenting an argument.

The Grammarly plagiarism checker software, which I am using now at EUCLID, is a reassuring way of avoiding plagiarism. Nonetheless, I will keep an eye on myself to avoid mistakes in adequately citing a source.

6) STYLE GUIDES

When I stumbled upon this concept of style guides, I was initially confused because, as the text rightly points out, there is not "a single authoritative source on style." I decided to refer to the book "The Elements of Style," which discusses the elementary rules of English usage, including how to use possessives in American and UK English styles (Jr, White, and Angell, 1912, 7). I find some rules in the book challenging to apply in actual texts, especially for a first-time Ph.D. student like myself.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic writing rules and guidelines exist to ensure fairness and transparency in the academic community. To avoid plagiarism, the student must adhere to these rules when producing his or her own work by acknowledging where the sources come from. Most importantly, the student must be equipped with the basics of the English language, such as the use of punctuation and sticking to either the American or UK style of English.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Euclid University. "Understanding templates and styles for ACA-401." March 2, 2016.

Vimeo video, 14:34.

https://vimeo.com/157480457?embedded=true&source=vimeo_logo&owner=12712423

Jr, William Strunk, E. B. White, and Roger Angell. 1912. *The Elements of Style*. Fourth Edition. Edited by Test Editor.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.